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**Improving the Quality of Education
to Strengthen the Global Competitiveness:
A Response to the Current Curriculum**

Presented by :

Palembang, May 16-18, 2014

Chief Editor: Hartono

**Faculty of Teacher Training and Education
Sriwijaya University
South Sumatra - Indonesia**

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The 1st Sriwijaya University Learning and Education International Conference
“Improving the Quality of Education to Strengthen the Global Competitiveness:
A Respond to the Current Curriculum”

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Faculty of Teacher Training and Education
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THE IMPLEMENTATION GENDER ANALYSIS PATHWAY (GAP) OF GENDER ORIENTED SCHOOL AT SMA IN KABUPATEN PENAJAM PASER UTARA

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Abstract

The focus of this research is the implementation of gender-oriented schools in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara, which has the following characteristics; a. The System of School Management: the leadership culture in schools is still dominated by male teachers, while in fact the number of female teachers is higher. b. Teaching and Learning Process: There is a gender bias in learning materials in all levels of education, for example in Indonesian Language, Social Science, Civics, and Illustration subject. These learning materials are mostly published by Erlangga and Tiga Serangkai. In general, the human resources in education do not understand the concept of gender, as the result there will be a negative impact due to the gender bias. c. The Role of Community through School Committee: The number of female representative in school committee is still low due to the structure of committee, such as the chairman and vice chairman, is dominated by male.

Keywords: Gender-oriented School, Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP)

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Problem

Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara is one of the fourteen regions/towns that have been implementing a Socialization of Gender-oriented School in 2010. This socialization was held in front of the headmasters and teachers from elementary school, junior high school, and senior high school. The aim of this socialization is to improve knowledge and as the outcome, the participants will implement gender-oriented in teaching learning process. However, still there is a gender inequality, for example female students usually have lack of courage to state their opinion. This may be due to the parents' habit when they suggest their daughter not to speak too loud, but in gentle voice. In contrast, their son may speak loudly. This suggestion will remain in children mind, as the result female students tend to shy to state their opinion, thus unconsciously it will develop the silent culture in schools.

If this condition continues, there will be a gender inequality that will not benefit female students and will be an obstacle in the human development quality especially in education. This research focused on the implementation of gender-oriented in senior high school by considering the students' age that more ready and easier to understand the concept of gender and also supported by the indication that the higher of education level, the lower of female involvement. The data presented in this paper will show the gender inequality in the implementation of gender-oriented schools.

For example, the classroom setting is important to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning process. There are several things that have been done in order to make the school tidier, for example by arranging furniture in certain position in the classrooms and laboratories, using illustrations/pictures on the wall, choosing a good quality of tables and chairs, and other physical infrastructure. However, there are schools that find it difficult to organize the classroom due to the limited facilities or the higher ratio of student in the classroom, as the result the sitting position unable to be changed. These conditions also make the students centered learning is hard to be achieved.

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Another difficulty is the teachers have no right to choose the furniture. Regardless of these limitations, innovative teachers have to find a way to organize the classroom to be more conducive to the growth of male and female students' participation.

In general, most of the teachers have not pay attention to the equality of opportunity and treatment to students with different gender through a classroom setting. As have been mention before female students, due to the influence of social culture, generally do not like to state their opinion loudly. The sitting positions that put them in the back or in the corner of the classroom will make them keep quiet and will influence their achievements.

The traditional classroom setting, all seats face forward, will not support the students-centered learning environment that believed as a very suitable approach to improve students' active participation in the classroom and their achievements.

Based on the data above, then the question is: Is there any gender issue in education in Kalimantan Timur, especially in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara?

Focus and Formulation of the Research

Based on the gender issues above, this research—Implementation of Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP) of Gender-oriented School in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara—focus on what, how, and why there is a gender-oriented high school in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara? Furthermore the main focus this research is divided into four sub focus.

The first sub focus deals with the question: how is the political will of the Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara government to the implementation of gender-oriented schools in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara.

The second sub focus deals with the question: how is the management of gender-oriented schools in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara? This question is the second sub focus because it may be an indicator of the characteristics of gender-oriented schools. This sub focus may be divided into four parts, which related to 1) the description of the school culture, 2) the human resource management, 3) schools' facilities and infrastructure, and 4) budget/funding.

The third sub focus deals with the question: how is the process of teaching learning in gender-oriented schools in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara? This third focus is related to 1) lesson plan, 2) learning materials, 3) learning method, 4) learning environment, 5) teachers/educators, 6) and the assessment of learning outcomes.

The fourth sub focus deals with the question: how is the community participation in actualizing the gender-oriented schools in Kabupaten Paser? This fourth sub focus is related to the community involvement both male and female in school activities and school committee, have a balanced in terms of access, roles, and responsibilities, and participate in the control function, take decision, and receive equal benefit.

RESEARCH METHOD

Concept of Gender

The word "gender" is derived from the English language, gender, which means "gender" (John M. Echols and Hassan Shadily, 1983: 265). In *Webster's New World Dictionary*, gender is defined as the apparent differences between male and female in terms of value and behaviour. To understand the concept gender we should differentiate the word gender and sex. The word "sex" differentiate two kinds of human sexes that determined biologically that attached to a particular sex (Oakley, 1972:12). This classification based on the physiological differences that related to

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reproductive function and prevailed to all human that can reproduce (Lott & Maluso, 1993). Lott and Maluso (1993: 99-123) stated that gender for human means all the complex attributes of male and female that comes from culture. Gender is constructed and learned from the conditions, experiences and certain possibilities that will be different across cultures, that is paired with femininity and masculinity, and this is the main social categories that used by most of people as the basis for socialization and to state social status (Davidson & Gordon, 1979; Lott & Maluso, 1993).

The statements above are in line with Edgar and Sedgwick (1999: 148) "The concept of 'gender' is typically placed in opposition to concept of 'sex'. While our sex (female/male) is a matter of biology, our gender (feminine/masculine) is a matter of culture."

Gender as social construction may be proved by the characteristics of the attributes that can be interchanged between male and female. These attributes may change over times, places, and levels (Fakih, 2001; Viswewaran, 1997). According to Fakih (2001: 45) these gender differences may be formed by several factors, such as being shaped, socialized, strengthened, and even constructed both socially and culturally through religious and national teachings.

Based on the statements above, it may be concluded that etimologically the meaning of gender is identical with the meaning of sex. While terminologically, gender and sex have a very different meaning, even though they are still related and can not be separated. Gender is the attributes that attached to male and female that may be interchanged and constructed by the culture. Thus, gender will depend on the social norm and value in determining how male and female behave.

Fakih (2001) mentioned that gender inequality is the condition where the relation between male and female is not equal, will disadvantage or even sacrifice one party. This inequality due to the ideology, structure, and the system of social and culture that require the gender stereotype that differentiate the role of male and female in various parts of life. Gender inequality is manifested in various types of inequality, such as marginalization or economic degradation, subordination or the belief that women are not important in political decision, stereotyped with negative label, violence, long work-hours, and socialization of ideological value in gender role (Fakih, 2001).

Gender-sensitive Perspective

The elimination of gender inequality may be done, for example, by implementing a gender-sensitive perspective in various parts of life (Callamard, 1999; Roop & Gere, 1989; Salgado, Vogt, King, & King, 2002; UNESCO, 2005). According to Callamard (1999) gender-sensitive perspective is characterized by: an understanding that the roles of male and female are not determined biologically, but by social system.

Definition of Gender Sensitivity

By using gender perspective above (Callamard, 1999), gender sensitivity is defined as the quality where there is a constant awareness that the different roles between male and female are not determined biologically, but by the complex environmental factors including economic, politic, social, religion, and cultural condition. The awareness that male and female have different experience, including having the different opportunities especially in term of access and control to resources and benefits, dan every individual have a heterogenous experience that can not be generalized. Also, the awareness that gender discrimination is systemic and may be manifested in various parts of life from the larger to smaller social structure.

Gender Equality

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Gender equality may also mean that there is a similar condition for male and female in obtaining opportunities and rights as human beings, in order to be able to contribute and participate in political activities, law, economic, social culture, education, national defense and the rights to experience the benefit of development. The manifestation of gender equality may be seen if there is no discrimination between male and female, have access, opportunity to participate, control over the development, and gain equal benefit of development. Having access means have the opportunity to use these resources. Having control means have authority to take decision to use these resources. Gender equality is one of the process and equal treatments to male and female.

Gender Mainstream in Education

The term gender mainstream is firstly introduced since the President Decree no. 9 in 2000, and then followed up by the Regulation of Ministry of Home Affairs no. 15 in 2008 and the Regulation of Ministry of National Education no. 84 in 2008 on the implementation of gender mainstream in education.

The concept of gender mainstream in the President Decree no.9 in 2000 on the guidelines for gender mainstream in national development mean as a strategy to integrate gender as one integral dimension of the planning, organizing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating to the policy and program of national development. Gender mainstream is implemented through gender analysis which means to identify and comprehend the reasons of gender inequality, including the problem solving and as a means of communication, information, and education that implemented to foster and improve the ability of the government institutions at central and regional about gender.

Gender-oriented School

A gender-responsive school is a social environment that takes into consideration the specific needs of male and female children in an equal way (Yulealawati, 2009: 1-27).

RESEARCH METHOD

This study is a qualitative study with GAP (Gender Analysis Pathway) as a method of analysis. Methods of data collection used participant observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation.

The variables and indicators of Insight School of Gender:

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No	Variable	Indicators	Sumber
1	2	3	4
1.	Perspective gender of manajement school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Management System is the Gender Perspective - Insightful Gender Classrooms - Management infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sekolah SMAN di Kab.PPU
2.	Gender Visionary School Learning Proses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning School Perspective of Gender • Learning the Gender Responsive Planning • Gender Responsive Learning Materials • Use of Gender Responsive language • Gender Responsive Classroom Interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disdik Kab. PPU • Sekolah SMA • Hasil Penelitian
3.	Community Participationin Achieving Gender Responsive Schools	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The school committee is responsive 2) Interaction with the parent teacher 3) Management of the Gender Responsive puberty Sexual Harassment 	Masyarakat/Komite Sekolah

This research is qualitative research with ethnographic as a method. In collecting the data, the researcher used participative observation, in-depth interview, and documentation. In analyzing the data, the researcher used Gender Analysis Pathway.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research findings, it may be concluded that gender-oriented school is one of the gender mainstream program in education that attempt to achieve gender equality in education (gender-responsive education). As one of the mainstream programs, gender-oriented school is not familiar by school community in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara. Four senior high schools as the setting of this research (SMAN I, SMAN II, SMAN III, and SMAN IV) have not implemented the gender-oriented school program due to the headmasters have not arranged the budget for gender-responsive in curriculum, syllabus, lesson plan, and especially in the objective and process of teaching and learning. Implementation of gender-oriented school in Kabupaten Penajam Paser may be described as follows:

System of School Management:

Based on the result of field survey in four schools—SMAN I, SMAN II, SMAN III, and SMAN IV—there are still found problems in the management of education, such as the leadership culture is still dominated by male teachers, in fact the number of female teacher is higher.

Number of Teachers		Level of Education				Position				Teaching Period			
		Bachelor degree (S1)		Master degree (S2)		< 4A		>4A		<20 years		>20 years	
M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
MAN I 31	46	27	41	4	3	20	34	3	12	10	14	21	32
MAN II 21	33	19	31	2	3	10	23	3	9	6	14	19	19
MAN III 26	29	21	22	2	1	16	12	5	9	19	28	7	1
MAN IV 14	22	16	20	2	-	7	2	7	12	4	1	10	21

- (2) The planning of school facilities and infrastructure are not designed to fulfil the specific needs of male and female, even though there are school facilities that separate male and female. For example, the toilet for male and female, prayer room is separated by using curtain for male and female. But still, ablution facility and medical room are not divided, for example in SMAN IV.
- (3) The management of human resources in schools are not gender-responsive, for example the opportunity to get a scholarship is mostly used by male teachers, and the schools are not sensitive to take affirmative action as a mechanism in order to force female teachers to take advantage of scholarship opportunity. As the result, the lower percentage of accredited female teachers than male teachers because their level of education is under the bachelor degree.

Teaching and Learning Process

- 1) There is still a gender bias in the learning materials in senior high school/ vocational high school (SMA), especially in text or discourse materials for example in several subjects such as Indonesian Language, social science, civics, and illustration. These learning materials generally taken from textbooks published by Erlangga and Tiga Serangkai.
- 2) In General the human resources (teachers) do not understand the concept of gender in learning materials, they tend to think that it is not urgent thing, but if it remains in students' mind it will influence their behavior.

The Role of Community through School Committee

The low representation of female teachers in school committee due to the structure of committee for example chairman and vice chairman is dominated by male teachers. This condition will influence school decision making where the structure of committee is mostly dominated by male teachers. This will also influence the decisions that unable to accommodate the female needs and aspiration at school which are different with male.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis with the research focus is the implementation of gender-oriented school in Kabupaten Penajam Paser Utara, there are the characteristics as follow:

- a. The System of School Management: the leadership culture in school is still patriarchal, dominated by male teachers, while in fact the number of female teachers is higher.
- b. There is still a gender bias in learning materials especially in the Indonesian Language, Social Science, Civics and Picture Illustration subject, so it is required teachers who understand the concept of gender-oriented in order to integrate the concept of gender-oriented in various learning materials.
- c. The low representation of female in school committee due to the structure of the committee, such as the chairman and vice chairman, is dominated by male.

RECOMENDATION

Based on the research findings, the researcher compiled the following recommendations:

- 1) The policy makers should explicitly support the acceleration of the implementation of gender mainstream (the institution internal instruction to all work units to implement the gender-responsive activities) in the field of education. This policy, as a reflection of political support from that relevant field, and/or to embodied in the vision and mission and the education development program that is gender-responsive.

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- 2) Kabupaten Paser Education Office should have a section in charge and responsible for the implementation of gender mainstream mechanism in the field of education in the education institution in order to improve the quality of education that is gender responsive.
- 3) The gender-oriented school program has to be implemented in all educational institutions from elementary, secondary, and even higher level of education. The Gender Research Centre of Mulawarman University along with Provincial Education Departement of Kalimantan Timur plan to implement the Model of Gender-oriented School in nine districs/cities with Kabupaten Paser as the pilot project.
- 4) To implement the model of gender-oriented school model, the human resources and all educational components should be gender responsive. The headmaster, teachers, educators, school committee, parents, and community as the human resources, and all components in education field such as curriculum, teaching materials, facilities and infrastructure in teaching and learning process should be gender responsive.
- 5) The decision makers in school environment ranging from planning, arranging, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation have to accommodate the interests of male and female human resources.
- 6) Refer to President Instruction no.9 in 2000 on Gender Mainstream in National Development, schools start from elementary, secondary, to higher level in fourteen districs and cities in Kalimantan Timur Province may implement the program of gender-oriented school.

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